

Determination of Mobility Ratios and Bi-ionic Potentials of Hemin Collodian Membrane Electrodes in Aqueous and Aquo-methanolic Media

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In continuation of our previous work¹, further attempts have been made to ascertain the utilities of membrane electrodes of hemin collodian in Br^- , I^- and NO_3^- forms in the determination of bi-ionic potentials. Lindenfeld² replaced electrovalently bound Cl^- ions of hemin with Br^- and I^- . The valid range of concentration in respective aqueous and aquo-methanolic electrolytic media has been determined.

Results and Discussion

Mobility ratios for Br^-/I^- , $\text{Br}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ and I^-/NO_3^- pairs at different concentrations were calculated using Willie and Kannan equation³. Mobility ratio values for Br^-/I^- in case of 0, 10 and 30% (v/v) aqueous and aquo-methanolic media are found to be 1.351, 1.349 and 1.350, for $\text{Br}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ are 1.528, 1.523 and 1.539, and for I^-/NO_3^- are 2.788, 2.802, 2.771 respectively. The valid range of concentration in aqueous and aquo-methanolic media is found to be 0.001–0.04 M in case of Br^-/I^- , $\text{Br}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ and I^-/NO_3^- at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Experimental

Hemin was prepared by reported method⁴. Membrane electrodes of hemin-collodian were prepared as reported earlier¹. The e.m.f. measurements were obtained using an Ajco potentiometer. Individual activities of various anions were obtained by graphical plotting⁶. Actual mobility ratios were calculated from bi-ionic potential measurements using Willie and Kannan equation³.

References

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